

Chemical Examination of the Leaves of *Dodonaea* *Viscosa* Linn

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Dodonaea viscosa Linn (Family *Sapindaceae*) is a common hedge plant found in the drier regions of India. Its leaves are used as antipyretic and in sore throat¹. Ghosh² could not isolate any crystalline compound from the leaves, but Kotake and Kuwata³ reported the isolation of a tricyclic monocarboxylic acid, hautriwaic acid, $C_{20}H_{28}O_4$, m.p. 182-84, $[\alpha]_D -104^\circ$, from the ether extract. Parihar and Dutt⁴ isolated from the seeds of the plant an aglycone, dodogenin, $C_{23}H_{36}O_6$, m.p. 249°, which was believed to be a steroidal saponin. As further work on the isolation and study of chemical constituents from this plant was not pursued, a reinvestigation of this species was undertaken.

The present preliminary study has resulted in isolation of β -sitosterol and stigmasterol from the unsaponifiable fraction of the benzene extract of the leaves and isochromanin from the ethanol extract, after acid hydrolysis.

Air-dried powdered leaves (2 kg.) of *D. viscosa* Linn were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus successively with benzene and 90% ethanol. The residue from the benzene extract was taken up in ether (1 litre) and the ether solution washed repeatedly (5 x 200 ml) with 2% NaOH to yield an acid fraction, the studies on which will be reported later. The dark green neutral fraction (20 g.) was hydrolysed under reflux for 6 hours with 5% ethanolic KOH and the unsaponifiable matter (4.2 g.) isolated with ether was chromatographed in benzene solution over alumina. After removal of traces of wax with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), subsequent elution with benzene and crystallisation of the residue from methanol yielded a sterol fraction (positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction) (200 mg.), m.p. 125-12°. It was converted into the benzoate and resolved by chromatography into two components which were crystallised from acetone as colorless flakes: (i) m.p. 145-46°, $[\alpha]_D -12.8^\circ$ (CHCl₃) (Found: C, 83.15; H, 10.88. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{42}O_2$: C, 83.39; H, 10.42%); (ii) m.p. 159-60°, $[\alpha]_D -25.2^\circ$ (CHCl₃) (Found: C, 83.44; H, 10.16. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{42}O_2$: C, 83.72; H, 10.07%).

β -Sitosterol.—The benzoate, m.p. 145-46°, on hydrolysis yielded a sterol, crystallising from methanol as flakes, m.p. 136-37°, $[\alpha]_D -34.4^\circ$ (CHCl₃); acetate as shining flakes

1. Hoeking, "A Dictionary of Terms in Pharmacognosy", p. 71, Charles C. Thomas, Springfield, Illinois, 1955.
2. Ghosh, *Indian Forests*, 1933, 59, 78.
3. Kotake and Kuwata, *Chem. Abs.*, 1937, 31, 1417.
4. Parihar and Dutt, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 26A, 56.

from chloroform-methanol, m.p. 125-26°. The sterol was identified as β -sitosterol by comparison with authentic samples of its acetate and benzoate.

Stigmasterol.—The sterol, obtained by hydrolysis of the benzate, m.p. 159-60°, crystallised from ethanol as plates, m.p. 166-67°, [α]_D-47.3° (CHCl₃); *acetate*, m.p. 142-43°. Mixed m.p. determinations with authentic samples of stigmasterol and its derivatives established the identity of the sterol.

Isorhamnetin.—The 90% ethanol extract of the leaves was concentrated *in vacuo* to remove most of the solvent and then treated with water. The aqueous solution, after rejecting a small quantity of an insoluble resin that separated, was repeatedly washed with ether and then hydrolysed for 3 hours with 7% H₂SO₄ (final acid conc.) and the precipitated solid Soxhleted with ether for 24 hours. A yellow pigment (2.5 g.) was obtained after trituration of the residue with ethanol. It developed an intense magenta-red colour with magnesium and EtOH-HCl and gave, on descending paper chromatography, a single spot [R_f , 0.75 and 0.68 with the upper layer of butanol²-acetic acid-water (4:1:5) and phenol saturated with water respectively] which turned bright yellow on exposure to ammonia, indicating it to be a flavonoid. It is sparingly soluble in most organic solvents. It crystallised from aqueous pyridine as yellow microcrystalline needles, m.p. 302-205° (deccmp.). It exhibited the colour reactions and had R_f values (including a mixed chromatogram with an authentic sample³) characteristic of isorhamnetin.

With acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate on the steam bath for 2 hours, the flavonol formed an acetate, crystallising from ethyl acetate-ethanol as colorless needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen⁵ of *isorhamnetin tetra-acetate*, 206-207°. (Found: C, 59.28; H, 3.84. Calc. for C₂₄H₂₀O₁₁: C, 59.5; H, 4.13%).

Methylation of the flavonol, using excess of dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous K₂CO₃ in dry acetone for 48 hours, gave *quercetin pentamethyl ether* as colorless needles from aqueous methanol, m.p. 150-51°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample⁵.

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